

Modified Hankel Matrix Approach for Model Order Reduction in Time Domain

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Abstract : The author presented a method for model order reduction of large-scale time-invariant systems in time domain. In this approach, two modified hankel matrices are suggested for getting reduced order models. The proposed method is simple, efficient and retains stability feature of the original high order system. The viability of the method is illustrated through the examples taken from literature.

Keywords : Model Order Reduction; Stability; Hankel Matrix; Time-Domain; Integral Square Error.

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